
An Estimate for Upper Bound of Maximum Modulus of Complex Polynomial

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Abstract Let $p(z)$ be a polynomial of degree n . In this paper we have obtained an inequality for the maximum modulus of a polynomial involving the coefficients of polynomial having all its zeros outside a disk of prescribed radius. Our result not only improves upon some well known results but also gives generalizations of some well known earlier proved inequalities.

Keywords Polynomials; complex domain; Inequalities; Zeros

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1. Introduction and Statement of Results

THEOREM 1.1. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n , then

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \leq n \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.1)$$

The result is best possible and equality holds for $p(z) = \lambda z^n$, $\lambda (\neq 0)$ being a complex number.

If we restrict ourselves to the class of polynomials having no zeros in $|z| < 1$, then inequality (1.1) can be sharpened. In fact in this case the following result was conjectured by Erdős and later verified by Lax [7].

THEOREM 1.2. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n , having no zeros in $|z| < 1$, then

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \leq \frac{n}{2} \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.2)$$

The result is best possible and equality in (1.2) holds for $p(z) = \lambda + \mu z^n$ where $|\lambda| = |\mu|$.

Simple proofs of this theorem were given by de-Bruijn [4] and Aziz and Mohammad [2]. For other proofs see Boas [3] and Rahman [9].

Inequality (1.2) was further improved by Aziz and Dawood [1] under the same hypothesis by proving the following result.

THEOREM 1.3. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n , which does not vanish in $|z| < 1$, then

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \leq \frac{n}{2} \left\{ \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| - \min_{|z|=1} |p(z)| \right\}. \tag{1.3}$$

The result is best possible and equality holds for $p(z) = \lambda + \mu z^n$, $|\lambda| = |\mu|$.

As a generalization of Theorem 1.2, Malik [8] proved the following

THEOREM 1.4. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n having no zeros in $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \leq \frac{n}{1+k} \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \tag{1.4}$$

The result is sharp and extremal polynomial is $p(z) = (z+k)^n$.

Various other results in the same sphere could be seen in literature (for references see [10], [11], [12]).

In the present paper, we prove the following result which provides improvement of the Theorem 1.4 due to Malik [8]. The theorem is also of independent interest and could be generalized into many other results. This result paves the path to other results too.

THEOREM 1.5. If $p(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^n a_\nu z^\nu$ is a polynomial of degree n , not vanishing in $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then for

$0 \leq r \leq \rho \leq k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{|z|=\rho} |p(z)| \leq & \left(\frac{\rho+k}{r+k} \right)^n \left[1 - \frac{k(k-\rho)(n|a_0| - k|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right] \max_{|z|=r} |p(z)| \\ & \times \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{k+r}{k+\rho} \right)^n \right\} \\ & - \frac{(\rho^n - r^n)}{k^{n-2}} \left\{ \frac{n|a_0| + \rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right\} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

2. Lemmas

LEMMA 2.1. If $p(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^n a_\nu z^\nu$ is a polynomial of degree n , having no zeros in $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \leq n \frac{n|a_0| + k^2|a_1|}{(1+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2|a_1|} \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \tag{2.1}$$

The above lemma is due to Govil, Rahman and Schmeisser [5].

LEMMA 2.2. If $p(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^n a_\nu z^\nu$ is a polynomial of degree n , having no zeros in $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| &\leq n \frac{n|a_0| + k^2|a_1|}{(1+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2|a_1|} \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| \\ &\quad - \frac{n}{k^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0| + k^2|a_1|}{(1+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2|a_1|} \right\} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

PROOF OF LEMMA 2.2. The lemma can be easily proved by replacing $p(z)$ by $F(z) = p(z) + \lambda m \frac{z^n}{k^n}$ in Lemma 2.1 and applying Rouché's theorem.

LEMMA 2.3. If $p(z) = \sum_{v=0}^n a_v z^v$ is a polynomial of degree n , not vanishing in $|z| < k, k > 0$, then for $0 \leq r \leq \rho \leq k$,

$$\max_{|z|=\rho} |p(z)| \leq \left(\frac{\rho+k}{r+k} \right)^n \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \tag{2.3}$$

The result is best possible and equality occurs for $p(z) = (z+k)^n$.

The above result is due to Jain [6].

3. Proof of the Main Theorem

PROOF OF THEOREM 1.5. Since $p(z)$ has no zeros in $|z| < k, k \geq 1$, therefore the polynomial $F(z) = p(tz)$, where $0 \leq t \leq k$, has no zeros in $|z| < k/t$, where $k/t \geq 1$. Applying Lemma 2.2 to the polynomial $F(z)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{|z|=1} |F'(z)| &\leq n \left\{ \frac{n|a_0| + \frac{k^2}{t^2} t|a_1|}{\left(1 + \frac{k^2}{t^2}\right)n|a_0| + 2\frac{k^2}{t^2} t|a_1|} \right\} \max_{|z|=1} |F(z)| \\ &\quad - \frac{n}{k^n/t^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0| + \frac{k^2}{t^2} t|a_1|}{\left(1 + \frac{k^2}{t^2}\right)n|a_0| + 2\frac{k^2}{t^2} t|a_1|} \right\} \min_{|z|=\frac{k}{t}} |F(z)|, \\ \max_{|z|=1} |p'(tz)|t &\leq nt \left\{ \frac{n|a_0|t + k^2|a_1|}{(t^2+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \max_{|z|=1} |p(tz)| \\ &\quad - \frac{nt^n}{k^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0|t^2 + k^2t|a_1|}{(t^2+k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$\max_{|z|=t} |p'(z)| \leq n \left\{ \frac{n|a_0|t + k^2|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \max_{|z|=t} |p(z)|$$

$$- \frac{nt^{n-1}}{k^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0|t^2 + k^2t|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|$$

Now, for $0 \leq r \leq \rho \leq k$ and $0 \leq \theta < 2\pi$, we have

$$|p(\rho e^{i\theta}) - p(re^{i\theta})| \leq \int_r^\rho |p'(te^{i\theta})| dt$$

which implies

$$|p(\rho e^{i\theta}) - p(re^{i\theta})| \leq \int_r^\rho n \left\{ \frac{n|a_0|t + k^2|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \max_{|z|=t} |p(z)| dt$$

$$- \int_r^\rho \frac{nt^{n-1}}{k^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0|t^2 + k^2t|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} m dt$$

$$\leq \int_r^\rho n \left\{ \frac{n|a_0|t + k^2|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} \left(\frac{k+t}{k+r} \right)^n \max_{|z|=r} |p(z)| dt$$

$$- \int_r^\rho \frac{nt^{n-1}}{k^n} \left\{ 1 - \frac{n|a_0|t^2 + k^2t|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} \right\} m dt,$$

by Lemma 2.3, and $m = \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|$.

The above inequality, for $0 \leq r \leq \rho \leq k$, gives

$$M(p, \rho) \leq \left[1 + \frac{n}{(k+r)^n} \int_r^\rho \frac{n|a_0|t + k^2|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} (k+t)^n dt \right] M(p, r)$$

$$- \frac{mn}{k^n} \int_r^\rho \left[t^{n-1} - \frac{n|a_0|t^2 + k^2t|a_1|}{(t^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2t|a_1|} t^{n-1} \right] dt$$

$$- \frac{mn}{k^n} \left[\frac{\rho^n - r^n}{n} - \frac{n|a_0|\rho^2 + k^2\rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2\rho|a_1|} \left(\frac{\rho^n - r^n}{n} \right) \right]$$

$$\leq \left[1 + \frac{(k+\rho)}{(k+r)^n} \left\{ \frac{n|a_0|\rho + k^2|a_1|}{(\rho^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right\} \left\{ (k+\rho)^n - (k+r)^n \right\} \right] M(p, r)$$

$$- \frac{(\rho^n - r^n)}{k^n} \left[1 - \frac{n|a_0|\rho^2 + k^2\rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2 + k^2)n|a_0| + 2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right] m$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \left[1 + \frac{(k+\rho)(n|a_0|\rho+k^2|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} + \frac{(k+\rho)(n|a_0|\rho+k^2|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \left(\frac{k+\rho}{k+r} \right)^n \right] M \\
&\quad - \frac{(\rho^n-r^n)}{k^n} \left[\frac{k^2n|a_0|+k^2\rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right] m \\
&\leq \left[\frac{(k-\rho)k(n|a_0|+k|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} + \left\{ 1 - \frac{k(k-\rho)(n|a_0|-k|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right\} \left(\frac{k+\rho}{k+r} \right)^n \right] M \\
&\quad - \frac{(\rho^n-r^n)}{k^{n-2}} \left[\frac{n|a_0|+\rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right] m \\
&= \left(\frac{k+\rho}{k+r} \right)^n \left[1 - \frac{k(k-\rho)(n|a_0|-k|a_1|)}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{k+\rho}{k+r} \right)^n \right\} \right] M(p,r) \\
&\quad - \frac{(\rho^n-r^n)}{k^{n-2}} \left[\frac{n|a_0|+\rho|a_1|}{(\rho^2+k^2)n|a_0|+2k^2\rho|a_1|} \right] m
\end{aligned}$$

from which the proof the THEOREM 1.5 follows.

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